

SHG PROMOTION UNDER DEENDAYAL ANTYODAYA YOJANA - NATIONAL RURAL LIVELIHOODS MISSION (DAY-NRLM) IN INDIA

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Abstract

A women's Self-Help Group (SHG), coming together on the basis of mutual affinity is the primary building block of the DAY-NRLM community institutional design. DAY-NRLM focuses on building, nurturing and strengthening the institutions of the poor women, including the SHGs and their Federations at village and higher levels. In addition, DAY-NRLM promotes livelihood institutions of rural poor. The mission provides a continuous hand-holding support to the institutions of poor for a period of 5 – 7 years till they come out of abject poverty. The community institutional architecture put in place under DAY-NRLM will provide support for a much longer duration and of a greater intensity. The paper analyzes the promotion of SHGs under National Rural Livelihood Mission in India in different states. The study also analyzes the data with regard to state wise target and achievements of SHG bank linkage under NRLM. The study found that around 11, 58,480 SHGs constituting 27.15 per cent were fresh/new SHGs and remaining 31, 09,110 SHGs constituting 72.85 per cent were renewal/repeat/enhanced SHGs.

Key Words: Bank-linkage, Disbursement, Target, Achievement

Introduction

Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Rural Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NRLM) is the flagship program of the Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD) for promoting poverty reduction through building strong institutions for the poor, particularly women, and enabling these institutions to access a range of financial services and livelihoods. DAY-NRLM adopts a demand-driven approach, enabling the States to formulate their own State-specific poverty reduction action plans. The blocks and districts in which all the components of DAY-NRLM would be implemented, either through the SRLMs or partner institutions or NGOs, would be the intensive blocks and districts, whereas the remaining would be non-intensive blocks and districts. National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM) is a restructured version of restructuring Swarnajayanti Gram Swarajgar Yojana (SGSY). NRLM was renamed as DAY-NRLM (Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Rural Livelihoods Mission) w.e.f. March 29, 2016.

NRLM has set out with an agenda to cover 7 Crore rural poor households, across 600 districts, 6000 blocks, 2.5 lakh Gram Panchayats and 6 lakh villages in the country through self-managed Self Help Groups (SHGs) and federated institutions and support them for livelihoods collectives in a period of 8-10 years. In addition, the poor would be facilitated to achieve increased access to their rights, entitlements, and public services, diversified risk, and better social indicators of empowerment. NRLM believes in harnessing the innate capabilities of the poor and complements them with capacities (information, knowledge, skills, tools, finance, and collectivization) to participate in the growing economy of the country.

The Mission

"To reduce poverty by enabling the poor households to access gainful self-employment and skilled wage employment opportunities, resulting in appreciable improvement in their livelihoods on a sustainable basis, through building strong grassroots institutions of the poor."

The Core Values

The programme is intended for the Inclusion of the poorest and meaningful role to the poorest in all the processes in the rural areas of India. It is introduced with the object of ensuring transparency and

accountability of all processes and institutions. It ensures ownership and the key role of the poor and their institutions in all stages-planning, implementation, and, monitoring. It is intended to inculcate community self-reliance and self-dependence.

NRLM implementation is in a Mission Mode. This enables -

- a. The shift from the present allocation-based strategy to a demand-driven strategy enabling the states to formulate their own livelihoods-based poverty reduction action plans,
- b. Focus on targets, outcomes, and time-bound delivery,
- c. Continuous capacity building, imparting requisite skills and creating linkages with livelihoods opportunities for the poor, including those emerging in the organized sector, and
- d. Monitoring against targets of poverty outcomes.

As NRLM follows a demand-driven strategy, the States have the flexibility to develop their livelihoods-based perspective plans and annual action plans for poverty reduction. The overall plans would be within the allocation for the state based on inter-se poverty ratios.

Benefits

The key benefits of the Scheme are as follows:

- ☞ One member (preferably a woman) from each rural poor household would be brought under the Self Help Group (SHG) network. Women SHG groups would have bank-linkage arrangements.
- ☞ SHGs would be federated at the village level and higher levels to provide space, voice and resources and to reduce dependence on external agencies.
- ☞ The Mission consists of four components, viz., (i) social mobilization, community institution, and capacity building; (ii) financial inclusion; (iii) livelihood promotion; and (iv) convergence.
- ☞ The participatory social assessment would be organized to identify and rank all households according to vulnerability. The ranking would be with reference to the poorest of the poor, single woman and woman-headed households, disabled, landless, and migrant labor and they would receive special focus.
- ☞ Training and capacity building of the poor, particularly in relation to managing the institutions, livelihoods, credit absorption, and creditworthiness.
- ☞ The Mission also supports the development of skills for rural youth and their placement, training, and self-employment through rural self-employment institutes (RSETIs), innovations, infrastructure creation, and market support.
- ☞ Provision of Revolving Fund as support to SHGs to strengthen their institutional and financial management capacity and build a good credit history.
- ☞ Provision of Community Investment Support Fund (CIF) in the intensive blocks to the SHGs through the Federations to advance loans and/or undertake common/collective socio-economic activities.
- ☞ Introduction of financial inclusion model, loaning from banks, association and coordination with banking/financial institutions, and coverage from loss of life, health, etc.
- ☞ Provision of Interest Subvention on loans availed by SHGs to cover the difference between the lending rate of the banks and 7%.
- ☞ Convergence with various ministries and agencies dealing with poverty reduction of rural poor.
- ☞ With highly decentralized planning; States will have liberty in developing their own action plan for poverty reduction.
- ☞ NRLM to have suitable linkages at the district level with District Rural Development Agencies (DRDAs) and Panchayat Raj Institutions (PRIs).

Key Features of the Scheme

The key features and components of the Scheme include:

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Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the programme design of the Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Rural Livelihoods Mission
2. To analyze state wise the new and old SHGs promoted and financially supported under Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Rural Livelihoods Mission

Review of Literature

Chatterjee, Shankar, (2016) carried out a study in Kolar district of Karnataka by contacting Self-help Group (SHGs) formed under Deendayal Antyaodaya Yojana- National Rural Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NRLM)/Aajeevika which is presently in implementation in the country. It is pertinent to mention that initially the name of the programme was National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM)/Aajeevika but from 26 February 2016, Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India through a notification has rechristened as Deendayal Antyaodaya Yojana so presently it is known as Deendayal Antyaodaya Yojana- National Rural Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NRLM). The study reveals that DAY-NRLM is yet to start with full swing in Kolar district, Karnataka. However,

by contacting the two SHGs formed and nurtured under DAY-NRLM the author observed that they were matured enough and earning substantially.

Pratima Rana and Neelam Bhardwaj (2020) in their paper made an attempt to examine and evaluate SHGs as change agents which has been designed systematically to create income generating opportunities, identifying predominant factors of empowerment and knowing the level of empowerment among the SHG members in Uttarakhand. The component of livelihood and livelihood security were also highlighted. The results of the study would pave the way for policy makers to frame suitable policies and strategies for implementing such movements in other districts of State for the well being of rural people. The study identified various constraints- Administrative constraints (majority of the respondents reported less number of working staff as a major constraint), Social constraints (reluctance of the members to take leadership role was the main constraint reported by SHG members), Empowering constraints (lack of freedom to take decisions and lack of equal treatment were reported as the major constraints), Management constraints (lack of space was the major constraint) and marketing constraints (transportation problems and lack of market information were reported as the major constraints).

Rukmini Tankha(2021) in his research article presents insights from a study and summarises good practices, strategies and innovations that were spearheaded by SHGs amidst the pandemic. Findings from the report provide early lessons from ground-level action taken and recommendations for strengthening women's leadership to respond to crises. The authors recognised that during COVID-19, it the far-flung network of National Rural Livelihood Mission's women's self-help groups, spanning the length and breadth of the country, could be leveraged to ensure prevention and containment of the virus in rural areas. According to author women's SHGs and their federated structures harbour tremendous potential because of the social capital and solidarity networks they possess.

Agrawal Deepak (2023) discussed various government schemes and programmes on rural development, sustainable development and Community development. The author briefly analysed the status of the schemes namely, Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Rural Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NRLM), Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY), Saansad Adarsh Gram Yojana (SAGY), Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana-Gramin (PMAY-G) and Shyama Prasad Mukherji Rurban Mission (SPMRM) etc. The author felt that in spite of various programmes and huge expenditure on rural development, the rural scenario is not very satisfactory. In fact, rural India can be the most powerhouses for national development. The author opines that without developing rural areas, the country can never claim to be developed. The author suggests that to make India internationally competitive and boost its economic growth a sustainable rural development is essential. Now an efficient sustainable rural development system is need of hour. According to author there is the need to make more implementation of policy and programmes of the government in this respect honestly and sincerely.

SHGs Promotion

The particulars with regard to state wise promotion of SHGs under National Rural Livelihood Mission in India are presented in table 1.

Table 1

State Wise Promotion of SHGs under NRLM-2022-23

S .No.	Stat/ UT Name	Total SHG Promoted Under NRLM					
		During the Financial Year			Cumulative		
		New	Pre NRLM/ Revived	Total	New	Pre NRLM/ Revived	Total
1	Andhra Pradesh		1948			1	
2	Assam	11309	7949	19258	140265	193867	334132
3	Bihar	1897	82	1979	1028471	26464	1054935
4	Chhattisgarh	37610	8661	46271	195121	59229	254350
5	Gujarat	15885	16039	31924	112704	155284	267988
6	Jharkhand	4049	635	4684	239508	32956	272464
7	Karnataka	16151	10003	26154	76031	178185	254216
8	Kerala	3814	116	3930	108462	145458	253920
9	Madhya Pradesh	52727	11316	64043	357151	68090	425241
10	Maharashtra	51162	11426	62588	465160	132374	597534
11	Odisha	6319	22862	29181	229651	299126	528777
12	Rajasthan	21534	67	21601	253266	6631	259897
13	Tamil Nadu	28709	740	29449	164809	153594	318403
14	Telangana	231	2816	3047	124824	314656	439480
15	Uttar Pradesh	110387	23750	134137	617342	87951	705293
16	West Bengal	114270	1630	115900	727283	325642	1052925
17	Haryana	6277	1144	7421	52954	3038	55992
18	Himachal Pradesh	6571	1911	8482	35377	6320	41697
19	Jammu and Kashmir	15735	17	15752	76973	101	77074
20	Punjab	7680	195	7875	38533	837	39370
21	Uttarkhand	15748	2138	17886	47737	6476	54213
22	Arunachal Pradesh	2192	63	2255	7529	240	7769
23	Manipur	3333	44	3377	7603	121	7724
24	Meghalaya	1844	36	1880	41710	2380	44090
25	Mizoram	1303	145	1448	7216	2134	9350
26	Nagaland	1134	13	1147	9885	4145	14030
27	Sikkim	154	5	159	1877	3597	5474
28	Tripura	11526	334	11860	32999	13190	46189
29	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	71	5	76	1077	96	1173
30	Goa	144	68	212	1442	2209	3651
31	Ladakh	26	1	27	504	5	509
32	Lakshadweep	1	0	1	326	2	328
33	Puducherry	611	0	611	3021	1205	4226
34	Dadra & Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu	134	0	134	887	31	918
	Grand Total	552486	124212	676698	5437087	2849306	8286393

Source: <https://nrlm.gov.in/shgReport.do?methodName=showPage>

It can be inferred from table 1 that in 2022-23 financial year highest number (1, 14,270) of new SHGs were promoted from West Bengal State. It is immediately followed by the Uttar Pradesh state with 110, 387 SHGs promoted in the 2022-23 financial year. In 8 States/Union Territories the new SHG promoted under NRLM in 2022-23 is less than 1000. With 1 new SHG promotion in 2022-23 Lakshadweep stood at the lowest rung of the ladder. With regard to revival of SHGs in 2022-23 under NRLM Uttar Pradesh State stood at the top of ladder 23, 750 SHGs revival. In this regard it is followed by Odisha and Gujarat in second and third places respectively. In case of revival in 2022-23 financial years, in 23 States/Union Territories it is less than 1000 SHGs. Among them in 3 Union Territories it is '0'. With regard to cumulative new SHGs promoted under NRLM the State of Bihar stood at the top of the ladder with 10,28,471 SHGs. It is followed by West Bengal and Uttar Pradesh in second and third places respectively. Here, 3 Union Territories registered less than 1000 SHGs. In case of cumulative revival of SHGs under NRLM the State of Andhra Pradesh tops the list with 6,23,672 SHGs and it is followed by West Bengal and Telangana States in second and third places respectively. On the whole 552486 new SHGs were promoted under NRLM in India in 2022-23 financial year. The share of new SHGs promoted in 2022-23 constitutes 10.16 per cent of cumulative new SHGs promoted under NRLM since the launching of programme. On the other hand 124, 212 SHGs were promoted in 2022-23. They constitute 4.36 per cent of cumulative SHGs revived under the scheme.

SHG Bank Linkage under NRLM

Table 2 furnishes the data with regard to state wise target and achievements of SHG bank linkage under NRLM in India.

Table 2
State Wise Target and Achievements of SHG Bank Linkage under NRLM -2022-23
(Amount Rs. in Lakhs)

S. No.	State/UT	Target SHGs			Total Disbursement Amt.	Total Outstanding Amt.	Achievement		
		Fresh SHG's	Repeat/Renewals/Enhancement	Total SHG's			Total SHG's	Total Disbursement Amt.	Total Outstanding Amt.
1		3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Andaman and Nicobar Islands	650	0	650	140	600	48	148.36	160.46
2	Andhra Pradesh	11,800	509,000	520,800	3,866,000.00	5,390,200.00	776,736	4,531,608.98	6,361,953.69
3	Arunachal Pradesh	1,750	430	2,180	2,250.00	3,500.00	617	1,172.96	1,738.21
4	Assam	95,000	39,430	134,430	154,000.00	160,300.00	134,936	324,241.52	337,460.83
5	Bihar	185,000	279,850	464,850	866,480.00	1,173,280.00	700,975	908,517.01	1,453,899.15
6	Chhattisgarh	37,500	48,500	86,000	106,500.00	115,000.00	94,405	131,938.12	151,397.12
7	Goa	1,520	1,000	2,520	4,510.00	6,710.00	1,183	5,647.92	6,257.99
8	Gujarat	65,000	32,500	97,500	72,000.00	65,000.00	37,805	51,027.81	54,871.69
9	Haryana	13,900	8,100	22,000	22,900.00	28,500.00	20,537	33,232.23	35,253.70
10	Himachal Pradesh	10,200	4,100	14,300	17,500.00	21,100.00	5,345	11,502.93	17,181.74
11	Jammu Kashmir	14,320	3,830	18,150	31,700.00	38,100.00	19,177	46,227.79	52,897.78
12	Jharkhand	75,050	101,950	177,000	200,510.00	202,820.00	177,260	247,611.92	306,987.37
13	Karnataka	28,980	464,020	493,000	2,101,100.00	2,284,800.00	766,308	2,295,734.61	2,233,251.32
14	Kerala	6,150	143,850	150,000	617,000.00	910,000.00	85,014	584,051.67	818,565.79
15	Ladakh	300	0	300	300	250	6	22	51.19
16	Lakshadweep	100	0	100	100	100	39	40.98	121.43
17	Madhya Pradesh	120,000	40,500	160,500	200,000.00	150,000.00	140,261	245,191.91	266,801.97
18	Maharashtra	85,200	106,200	191,400	439,200.00	502,000.00	239,161	582,102.73	624,300.56
19	Manipur	1,300	800	2,100	3,200.00	2,500.00	1,579	2,575.98	3,040.58
20	Meghalaya	7,000	2,600	9,600	14,000.00	10,000.00	6,703	7,567.73	11,134.12
21	Mizoram	2,080	3,350	5,430	5,900.00	6,150.00	1,053	2,808.35	5,570.68
22	Nagaland	2,600	2,300	4,900	5,900.00	8,300.00	695	1,451.30	7,236.80
23	Odisha	45,000	203,000	248,000	511,200.00	663,000.00	344,583	867,896.10	922,945.95
24	Puducherry	1,200	3,600	4,800	14,750.00	23,100.00	2,438	12,406.83	17,479.54
25	Punjab	10,000	4,000	14,000	19,000.00	12,000.00	9,627	9,405.79	8,778.44
26	Rajasthan	55,000	36,100	91,100	144,000.00	104,000.00	83,906	140,284.35	139,968.50
27		3,000	1,200	4,200	5,000.00	5,000.00	1,203	3,032.29	3,041.22
28	Tamil Nadu	5,300	210,000	215,300	978,500.00	1,309,400.00	210,900	1,134,555.52	1,491,950.97
29	Telangana	6,880	333,800	340,680	1,754,000.00	2,341,000.00	308,626	1,530,095.60	2,214,547.05
30	Dadra&Nagar Haveli and Daman & Diu	300	0	300	180	90	85	69.09	90.02
31	Tripura	6,000	12,800	18,800	23,000.00	22,200.00	18,098	28,992.69	29,666.41
32	Uttarakhand	10,400	7,600	18,000	19,600.00	14,400.00	20,358	18,529.50	16,247.44
33	Uttar Pradesh	150,000	52,000	202,000	175,000.00	80,000.00	116,795	142,067.66	103,639.32

Source: <https://nrlm.gov.in/shgReport.do?methodName=showPage>

The data in table 2 shows that at national level the target under SHG bank linkage is 42,67,590 SHGs as on 31st March 2023. Among them 11, 58,480 SHGs constituting 27.15 per cent were fresh/new SHGs and remaining 31, 09,110 SHGs constituting 72.85 per cent were renewal/repeat/enhanced SHGs. With regard to total SHG target West Bengal state tops the list 5, 22,700 and it is followed by Andhra Pradesh (5, 20, 800) and Karnataka (4,93,000). The share of these three states together is 36.37 per cent in total SHGs at national level. The average amount disbursed per SHG at national is Rs.3.27 lakhs. With regard to average amount disbursed per SHG is highest in the state of Andhra Pradesh (Rs. 7.27 lakhs) and it is followed by Telangana (Rs. 5.15 lakhs) and Tamil Nadu (Rs. 4.54 lakhs). In 6 states/ Union Territories the average amount per shg is less than Rs. 1 lakh. The average outstanding amount per SHG at national level is Rs. 3.27 lakhs. In this regard once again top place is occupied by Andhra Pradesh (Rs.10.35 lakhs) and it is followed by Telangana (Rs. 6.57 lakhs) and

Tamil Nadu (Rs. 6.08 lakhs). At national level the achievement of linking of SHGs to banks under bank linkage programme under NRLM is more than 100 per cent. In 11 States /Union Territories it is 100 or more than 100 per cent. The disbursal percentage under Bank Linkage programme is 112.24 per cent at national level. In 12 States /Union Territories it is more than 100 per cent. With regard to achievement under outstanding amount is 112.74 per cent at national level. It is more than 100 per cent in 20 States /Union Territories.

Conclusion

The variation in performance across states likely reflects differences in implementation, rather than in the effectiveness of inputs provided by the programme. The NRLM took on the difficult challenge of changing lives in India's poorest regions not just by a large infusion of funds, but also by addressing extremely low levels of schooling and capabilities. The uniqueness of the programme, and its most innovative feature, was a design mechanism that paid attention to the constraints that plague most programmes when they move from pilot to scale: the lack of both financial and human capital.

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